

Full Length Research Paper

Profitability Assessment of Irrigated Crop Production among Small-Scale Farmers in Gombe State, Nigeria

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Received 19 May 2019; Accepted 22 June, 2019

The study examines profitability assessment of irrigated crop production among small-scale farmers in Gombe State, Nigeria. Data were collected from 180 irrigated crop farmers who were purposively and randomly selected from eight Local Government Areas in Gombe State using structured questionnaires. Data were analyzed using farm budgeting model. The result revealed that sole tomato enterprise has the highest gross margin and net farm

income of N193, 149.59 and N175, 891.53 per hectare respectively. High cost of labour, inadequate and high cost of fertilizer, inability to access bank loans among others were the major constraints faced by the farmers. Small-scale irrigation farming is profitable with potentials for increased productivity.

Keywords: Profitability, irrigation, small-scale farmers

INTRODUCTION

Irrigation has been defined as the application of water to the soil for the purpose of supplying moisture essential for plant growth. It is undertaken to provide an insurance against droughts, for cooling the soil and atmosphere. It is a science of planning and designing a water supply system, usually man made, for agricultural land to produce crops where there is virtually little or no precipitation and to protect the crops from bad effect of drought or low rainfall (Oladimeji and Abdulsalam, 2014). Irrigation is therefore regarded as a powerful factor in increasing crop productivity, more stable incomes and employment and for increasing prospects for multiple cropping and crop diversification (Oruonye, 2011). The establishment of large scale irrigation scheme in Nigeria is highly capital intensive and requires the expenditure of huge sums of money in an already scarce foreign exchange. Scientific advances have led to the development of productivity-increasing inputs such as inorganic fertilizer, improved seed and agrochemicals (Yakubu and Mohammed, 2018).

Small scale irrigation involves small holder farmers who

cultivate between 0.5 hectare (ha) and 1.0 ha of fadama lands during the dry season (Umar, 2016). They use water pumps to draw water from streams/rivers, lakes, boreholes, tube wells ponds for irrigation and take responsibility for investment and management of their farms (Umar, 2016). Many families in Nigeria cultivate small areas in fadama during the dry season, using water manually drawn from shallow wells or streams (Food and Agricultural Organization FAO, 2005).

Profit is defined as the difference between total revenue and total cost of production. The total cost (TC) is made up of variable cost (VC) and fixed cost (FC). Variable cost is the cost of inputs such as seeds, fertilizer, chemicals, hired labour, harvesting which are used up during the production period. Fixed cost are cost of inputs such as machineries, building, lands which are not used up during the production period (Olukosi and Ogunbible, 1989). The gross margin (GM) is used to determine profitability of crop production. Olukosi and Erhabor, (1988) defined gross margin as the difference between the gross farm income (GFI) and the total

variable cost (TVC), i.e. $GM = GFI - TVC$. It is used as a proxy measure of profitability on the assumption that fixed costs of production are negligible.

The World Bank (2001) in its evaluation of Kano and Sokoto State Agricultural Development Projects stated that reduction in transportation cost between the project areas and the major urban markets of the south due to improved transport service has made the dry season Fadama production of onion, peppers, garlic and tomatoes to be very profitable. The profitability of the dry season irrigation resulted in a rapid expansion in the use of motorized pumps. Alamu *et al.* (2002) found irrigated tomato and pepper under the Fadama development programme in Kaduna State of Nigeria, is profitable. They found out that the net return from a hectare of sole tomato was almost as much as what was expended on its production. Maurice *et al.* (2005) analyzed the profitability of rice-based cropping patterns among dry season fadama farmers in Adamawa State, Nigeria using gross margin analysis. They found out that sole rice enterprise was the most profitable among the enterprises with a gross margin of ₦38, 597.13 per hectare followed by rice/maize and rice/cocoyam enterprises which have gross margins per hectare of ₦32, 200.15 and ₦27, 635.50 respectively. Ohikere and Egeh, (2012) studying the small-scale irrigation farming in Kogi State found out that fadama cultivation has a higher net farm income (NFI) for all enterprises in the area which included ₦29,583.16/ha for sole paddy rice, ₦6,944.30/ha for sole sugar cane, ₦6,012.58/ha for Tomato/Pepper and cassava/potato mixtures. Usman and Bakari, (2013) studied the profitability of Small Scale Dry Season Tomato Production in Adamawa State, Nigeria and found out that tomato production was profitable with an estimated total cost of production and gross margin of ₦137, 092.86 and ₦138, 970.46 respectively. Ayoola, (2014) studied the comparative economic analysis of tomato under irrigation and rain-fed systems in some selected Local Government Areas of Kogi and Benue States, Nigeria. The result showed that gross margins obtained per hectare of tomato crop under irrigation and rain-fed systems were ₦153, 500 and ₦68, 000 respectively. The net profit per hectare was ₦128, 750 and ₦57, 050 for the irrigated and rain-fed systems respectively. The result indicated that investment in tomato crop production under irrigation system was worthwhile as it yielded greater revenue in excess of operational and overhead expenses in comparison with that of rain-fed system.

Oladimeji and Abdulsalam, (2014) made an economic analysis of dry season irrigated farming in Asa River, Kwara State, Nigeria. The profitability was measured as both the gross and net margins. Both total cost and gross margin showed that dry season irrigated farming was less costly and more profitable compared to rain fed farming. Average net margin was about 11% higher among the irrigated unit than the rain-fed farming. Profitability ratios

also showed irrigated farming profit margin, gross ratio and return on investment to be 0.49, 0.51 and 1.96 respectively and were found to be higher than the rain-fed of 0.46, 0.54 and 1.84 respectively (Umar, 2016). Profit in agricultural production is affected by the cost of inputs used. There is a relationship therefore between the cost of inputs and profit level of farmers. Cost of inputs increases the cost of production thereby reducing profit margin. Subsidizing improved agricultural inputs such as fertilizer, seeds and agrochemicals will highly reduce the total cost of production consequently increasing profit. Aboki, (2012) used the double-log profit model in the Taraba State cassava farmers and found out that the cost of cassava cuttings cost of hired labour and cost of mechanization adversely affected the profit of cassava farmers. This study examined the profitability of irrigated crop production as well as identifies different cropping systems among small scale farmers.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Gombe States, Nigeria. Gombe State lies between latitudes 9°30' and 12°30' north of the equator and between longitudes 8°45' and 11° 45' east of the Greenwich meridian. It shares boundaries with Bauchi State to the west, Taraba and Adamawa States to the south west, Borno State to the east and Yobe State to the north (Gombe State Ministry of Economic Planning GSMOEP 2014). The state has a land area of 20, 265 km² with a population figure of 1.85 million people (National Population Commission, 2006). The projected 2015 population figure is 2,321,195.69 people using 2.83% annual population growth rate. Gombe State is divided into eleven (11) Local Government Areas (LGAs). Gombe State is characterized by two distinct wet and dry seasons. The mean annual rainfall ranges from 600 mm to 1200 mm with the minimum and maximum temperatures of 22.7°C and 33.5°C respectively (Gombe State Economic Empowerment Strategies GOSEEDS 2006). The vegetation of Gombe State is open savannah woodland with trees occurring singly or in clusters. The state is traversed by river Gongola and numerous tributaries that are seasonal. There are also facilities for irrigation which include Dadin Kowa multipurpose Dam, Balanga Dam and Cham Dam. The major ethnic groups are Fulani, Tangale, Waja, Tera, Pero, Bolawa, Tula, Chamawa, Lunguda, Dadiya, Kamo and Awak Kanuri.

Sampling procedure and sampling size

A multi-stage sampling technique was used in this study. In the first stage, eight (8) LGAs were purposively selected based on their importance and intensity in irrigation farming. The LGAs selected were Dukku,

Table 1. Cost and returns per hectare of irrigated crop farmers.

Crop enterprise	Variable input	Variable cost (₦/ha)	% share in TVC/ha	Returns (₦)
Sole tomato	Fertilizer	4,216.13	5.88	GR/ha: 264,798.39
	Seeds	5,164.52	7.21	GM/ha: 193,149.59
	Labour	39,174.60	54.68	TFC/ha: 17,258.06
	Agrochemicals	1,482.26	2.07	TC/ha: 88,906.86
	Fuel(128 lit/ha)	12,800	17.86	NFI/ha: 175,891.53
	Eng.oil(5.6lit//ha)	2,800	3.91	
	Transport	6,011.29	8.39	
	TVC/ha	71,648.8		
Sole pepper	Fertilizer	6,155.17	11.02	GR/ha: 219,348.07
	Seeds	3,420.69	6.12	GM/ha: 163,483.89
	Labour	24,896.45	44.57	TFC/ha: 9,724.14
	Agrochemicals	2,648.28	4.74	TC/ha: 65,588.87
	Fuel(128 lit/ha)	12,800	22.91	NFI/ha: 153,759.75
	Eng.oil(5.6lit/ha)	2,800	5.01	
	Transport	3,144.14	5.63	
	TVC/ha	55,864.73		
Sole maize	Fertilizer	8,727.20	16.13	GR/ha: 117,480.57
	Seeds	3,863.43	7.14	GM/ha: 63,389.82
	Labour	18,512.20	34.22	TFC/ha: 9,384.87
	Agrochemicals	3,924.41	7.26	TC/ha: 63,475.62
	Fuel(120 lit/ha)	12,000	22.18	NFI/ha: 54,004.95
	Eng.oil(4.5lit/ha)	2,250	4.16	
	Transport	4,813.51	8.90	
	TVC/ha	54,090.75		

Source: Field Survey, 2014.

Kwami, Nafada, Funakaye, Akko, Yalmatu/Deba, Balanga, and Kaltungo. The second stage involved purposive selection of twenty four (24) farming communities based on their involvement in irrigation farming. Final stage involved random selection of 180 respondents in the 24 farming communities based on the list of farmers obtained from Gombe Agricultural Development Programme (GADP).

Model specification

Data obtained were subjected to farm budgeting model. This tool was used to determine the profitability of irrigation farming in Gombe State. The gross margin (GM) and the net farm income (NFI) that made up farm budgeting model (Olukosi and Erhabor, 1988) are expressed as:

$$GM = \sum Q_y P_{y_i} - \sum x_i P_x \quad 1$$

Where:

- GM = Gross margin (₦/ ha)
- Q_y = output from the various crops (kg)
- P_{y_i} = Unit price of the output per 100kg bag
- Q_{y_i}P_{y_i} = Total revenue from all the crops produced (₦/ha)
- x_i = Quantity of the variable inputs used (kg/ha and man-

- days/ha)
- Px_i = prices of the variable inputs used (₦/kg and man-days/ha)
- ∑Px_i = Total variable cost spent on variable inputs per hectare (₦)
- ∑ = Summation sign

$$NFI = GM - TFC \quad 2$$

Where:

- NFI = Net farm income (₦)
- TFC = Total fixed cost (₦)

The annual depreciation cost on farm tools and implement owned by the irrigation farmers was calculated using the straight line method (Olukosi and Erhabor, 1988) as follows:

$$D = \frac{P - S}{N} \quad 3$$

Where

- D = Depreciation value in (₦)
- P = Cost of implement or tools in (₦)
- S = Salvage value of implement or tool in (₦) at 10% of its cost
- N = Useful life of implement or tool in years

Table 2. Cost and returns per hectare of irrigated crop farmers.

Crop enterprise	Variable input	Variable cost (₦/ha)	% share in TVC/ha	Returns (₦)
Sole rice	Fertilizer	8,881.46	17.01	GR/ha: 126,591.47
	Seeds	5,257.07	10.07	GM/ha: 74,380.64
	Labour	15,875.96	30.41	TFC/ha: 5,046.78
	Agrochemicals	4,646.34	8.90	TC/ha: 57,257.61
	Fuel(118 lit/ha)	11,800.00	22.60	NFI/ha: 69,333.86
	Eng.oil (4.5lit/ha)	2,250.00	4.31	
	Empty sacks	3,500.00	6.70	
	Transport	4,646.34	8.90	
	TVC/ha	52,210.83		
Tomato/pepper	Fertilizer	9,764.71	19.80	GR/ha: 216,467.65
	Seeds	4,776.47	9.69	GM/ha: 167,152.94
	Labour	13,544.12	27.46	TFC/ha: 6,941.18
	Agrochemicals	2,923.53	5.93	TC/ha: 56,255.89
	Fuel(128 lit/ha)	12,800.00	25.96	NFI/ha: 160,211.79
	Eng.oil(5.6lit/ha)	2,800.00	5.68	
	Transport	2,705.88	5.49	
	TVC/ha	49,314.71		
Tomato/maize	Fertilizer	7,089.67	16.42	GR/ha: 191,743.61
	Seeds	4,086.63	9.46	GM/ha: 148,564.12
	Labour	8,297.87	19.22	TFC/ha: 7,112.46
	Agrochemicals	5,276.60	12.22	TC/ha: 50,291.95
	Fuel (120 lit/ha)	12,000.00	27.79	NFI/ha: 141,451.66
	Eng.oil (5.5lit/ha)	2,750.00	6.37	
	Transport	3,678.72	8.52	
	TVC/ha	43,179.49		

Source: Field Survey, 2014.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profitability of irrigated crop production

The results of profitability for the different crop enterprises are presented in (Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5). The Tables present the GM/ha and NFI/ha of fourteen (14) crop enterprises. Sole tomato enterprise had the highest GM/ha of ₦193, 149.59 with a NFI/ha of ₦175, 891.53 followed by Tomato/rice which has GM/ha of ₦175, 732.26 with a NFI/ha of ₦169, 389.93. However, tomato/maize/rice has GM/ha of ₦167, 789.46 with a NFI/ha of ₦161, 251.00. The rise in the gross margin of tomato could be possible because of its high market demand. Maize/rice enterprise had the least GM/ha of ₦56, 337.90 with a NFI/ha of ₦53, 489.24. The demand for irrigated cereal crops was not as high as that of vegetables. The TVC/ha in all the enterprises ranged from ₦42, 885.00 for tomato/pepper/rice to ₦71, 648.80 for sole tomato. During peak production periods, cost of farm inputs such as seeds, agrochemicals and hired labour are costly due to demand and competition. The labour variables had the highest percentage of the total variable cost per hectare (except in the tomato/maize, tomato/pepper/rice and pepper/maize/rice enterprises). It ranged from 19% in the tomato/maize enterprise to 55%

in the sole tomato enterprise. TFC/ha in all the enterprises also ranged from ₦2, 447.55 in pepper/maize/rice enterprise to ₦17, 258.06 in sole tomato enterprise. Sole tomato enterprise had the highest TC/ha of ₦88, 906.86 while tomato/pepper/rice had the least with ₦48, 478.14. The NFI/ha of ₦175, 891.53 and the TC/ha of ₦88, 906.86 for sole tomato enterprise showed that the profit from a hectare was almost double of what was expended on its production. The NFI/ha in all the enterprises were positive revealing that irrigation farming was profitable among the respondents.

Constraints faced by irrigation

Results in Table 6 itemized the constraints facing the irrigated crop farmers. The problems were ranked on the basis of their severity. These include high cost of labour, inadequate and high cost of fertilizer, and inability to access bank loans, pest and diseases among others. The result agrees with the finding of Haruna, (2005) who identified inadequate credit, high cost of input, pest and diseases, post-harvest crop loses inadequate marketing outlets and conflicts with pastoralists as major constraints facing farmers within the Fadama User Association in Bauchi State.

Table 3. Cost and returns per hectare of irrigated crop farmers.

Crop enterprise	Variable input	Variable cost (₦/ha)	% share in TVC/ha	Returns (₦)
Tomato/rice	Fertilizer	8,541.67	18.14	GR/ha: 222,811.43
	Seeds	4,416.67	9.38	GM/ha: 175,732.26
	Labour	13,387.50	28.44	TFC/ha: 6,333.33
	Agrochemicals	3,733.33	7.93	TC/ha: 53,412.50
	Fuel(119 lit/ha)	11,900.00	25.28	NFI/ha: 169,398.93
	Eng.oil(4.2lit/ha)	2,100.00	4.46	
	Empty sacks	3,000.00	6.37	
	Transport	4,750.00	10.09	
	TVC/ha	47,079.17		
Pepper/maize	Fertilizer	6,710.14	14.03	GR/ha: 197,795.48
	Seeds	3,260.87	6.82	GM/ha: 149,966.79
	Labour	16,140.29	33.75	TFC/ha: 3,900.67
	Agrochemicals	3,386.96	7.08	TC/ha: 51,729.36
	Fuel(123 lit/ha)	12,300.00	25.72	NFI/ha: 146,066.12
	Eng.oil(5.0lit/ha)	2,500.00	5.23	
	Transport	3,530.43	7.38	
	TVC/ha	47,828.69		
Maize/rice	Fertilizer	9,427.80	18.37	GR/ha: 107,665.52
	Seeds	3,557.33	6.93	GM/ha: 56,337.90
	Labour	15,482.15	30.16	TFC/ha: 2,839.66
	Agrochemicals	5,210.34	10.15	TC/ha: 54,167.28
	Fuel(118 lit/ha)	11,800.00	22.99	NFI/ha: 53,489.24
	Eng.oil(5.1lit/ha)	2,550.00	4.97	
	Empty sacks	3,300.00	6.43	
	Transport	3,093.10	6.03	
	TVC/ha	51,327.62		

Source: Field Survey, 2014.

Table 4. Cost and returns per hectare of irrigated crop farmers.

Crop enterprise	Variable input	Variable cost (₦/ha)	% share in TVC/ha	Returns (₦)
Tomato/pepper/ Maize	Fertilizer	8,687.10	18.80	GR/ha: 186,933.88
	Seeds	1,536.66	3.33	GM/ha: 140,736.69
	Labour	15,209.38	32.92	TFC/ha: 3,673.33
	Agrochemicals	1,406.90	3.05	TC/ha: 49,870.52
	Fuel(130 lit/ha)	13,000.00	28.14	NFI/ha: 137,063.36
	Eng.oil(5.6lit/ha)	2,800.00	6.06	
	Transport	3,557.15	7.70	
	TVC/ha	46,197.19		
	Tomato/pepper/ Rice	Fertilizer	3,500.00	8.16
Seeds		6,400.00	14.92	GM/ha: 136,535.10
Labour		11,385.00	26.55	TFC/ha: 5,593.14
Agrochemicals		2,800.00	6.53	TC/ha: 48,478.14
Fuel(129 lit/ha)		12,900.00	30.08	NFI/ha: 130,941.96
Eng.oil(5.6lit/ha)		2,800.00	6.53	
Empty sacks		3,100.00	7.23	
Transport		3,870.00	9.02	
TVC/ha		42,885.00		
Tomato/maize/ Rice	Fertilizer	9,878.85	18.78	GR/ha:220,384.65
	Seeds	3,846.18	7.31	GM/ha: 167,789.46
	Labour	16,062.46	30.54	TFC/ha: 6,538.46
	Agrochemicals	4,207.70	8.00	TC/ha: 59,133.65
	Fuel(129 lit/ha)	12,900.00	24.53	NFI/ha: 161,251.00
	Eng.oil(5.8lit/ha)	2,900.00	5.51	
	Empty sacks	2,800.00	5.32	
	Transport	2,703.85	5.14	
	TVC/ha	52,595.19		

Source: Field Survey, 2014.

Table 5. Cost and returns per hectare of irrigated crop farmers.

Crop enterprise	Variable input	Variable cost (₦/ha)	% share in TVC/ha	Returns (₦)
Pepper/maize/ Rice	Fertilizer	8,199.30	16.81	GR/ha: 195,897.57
	Seeds	4,195.80	8.60	GM/ha: 147,120.65
	Labour	12,837.41	26.32	TFC/ha: 2,447.55
	Agrochemicals	4,594.41	9.42	TC/ha: 51,224.47
	Fuel(130 lit/ha)	13,000.00	26.65	NFI/ha: 144,673.10
	Eng.oil(5.8 lit/ha)	2,900.00	5.64	
	Empty sacks	2,800.00	6.56	
	Transport	2,396.85	4.91	
	TVC/ha	48,776.92		
Tomato/pepper/ Maize/rice	Fertilizer	7,776.41	14.86	GR/ha: 181,913.73
	Seeds	4,199.55	8.03	GM/ha: 129,586.90
	Labour	17,315.29	33.09	TFC/ha: 3,750.66
	Agrochemicals	4,035.58	7.71	TC/ha: 56,077.49
	Fuel(131 lit/ha)	13,100.00	25.03	NFI/ha: 125,836.24
	Eng.oil(6.0 lit/ha)	3,000.00	5.73	
	Empty sacks	2,900.00	5.54	
	Transport	2,737.33	5.23	
	TVC/ha	52,326.83		

Source: Field Survey, 2014.

Table 6. Constraints of irrigated crop production.

Constraints	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
High cost of labour	251	11.49	1
Inadequate & high cost of fertilizer	240	10.98	2
Inability to access bank loan	212	9.70	3
Pest and diseases	198	9.06	4
Low prices of farm produce	187	8.56	5
Lack of improved seeds	169	7.73	6
Insufficient labour	165	7.55	7
Unavailability of good storage facilities	152	6.96	8
High cost of agrochemicals	139	6.36	9
Inadequate research & extension service	139	6.36	9
Clashes with pastoralists	117	5.35	10
Land tenure problems	116	5.31	11
Soil degradation	100	4.58	12
Total observations	2,185**	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2014. ** Multiple responses were allowed

Conclusion

Based on the findings, fourteen crop enterprises were identified in the study area. Small-scale irrigation farming was profitable in all the enterprises identified. However, sole tomato constitute high gross margin and net farm income compare to other enterprises. The major constraints encountered were high cost of labour, inadequate and high cost of fertilizer, inaccessibility to bank loan among others. If farmers' specific factors are addressed and inputs such as agrochemicals and quality seeds are increased it can go a long way in increasing the output of the farmers thereby increasing their profits. Government should strengthen farmers to participate in dry season farming by providing inputs at subsidize rate and timely.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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